

OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS THROUGH DISTANCE LEARNING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7804617>

Ochilova Shahlo G'ulomjon Qizi

*Uzbek State University of World Languages,
Faculty of Foreign Languages and Literature, 2nd year master's degree*

Annotation: *Independent work is very important in higher education. Students can also do independent work in distance learning conditions. The article is devoted to the organization of independent work of students with the help of Internet technology.*

Keywords: *independent education, distance education, internet technologies, method, student.*

Annotatsiya: *Oliy ta'limda mustaqil ishlar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Talabalar masofaviy ta'lim sharoitida ham mustaqil ishlarni bajarishning turli imkoniyatlariga ega. Maqola Internet texnologiyalari yordamida talabalarning mustaqil ishlarini tashkil etishga bag'ishlangan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *mustaqil ta'lim, masofaviy ta'lim, internet texnologiyalari, metod, talaba.*

Аннотация: *Самостоятельная работа очень важна в высшем образовании. Студенты также могут выполнять самостоятельную работу в условиях дистанционного обучения. Статья посвящена организации самостоятельной работы студентов с помощью интернет-технологий.*

Ключевые слова: *самостоятельное обучение, дистанционное обучение, интернет-технологии, метод, студент.*

INTRODUCTION

The current state of socio-economic development of society in Uzbekistan makes high demands on the quality of education. Modern personnel must have comprehensive information on a wide range of issues in different fields of science, its knowledge must be fundamental, professionally and practically oriented.

The main criterion for the effectiveness of the work of a higher educational institution is the high level of training of specialists. The quality of specialist training must meet the requirements established in the State Educational Standards and the requirements of the labor market.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The high quality of teaching is possible due to the strict selection of educational material and the use of active teaching methods that contribute to the formation of such knowledge in students that may have practical value in their future professional activities. The organization of the learning process, its implementation and further use of a specialist determines the quality of his training. It is possible to achieve a radical

improvement in the quality of training a specialist in higher education through the introduction of modern pedagogical and information technologies, which are a necessary requirement in the field of professional activity.

In connection with the trend of recent years to reduce classroom hours, independent work of students is becoming more and more relevant. According to the new standards, the proportion of extracurricular independent work of students is about 50%, that is, it is quite significant in the process of studying the discipline. Consequently, extracurricular independent work of students needs the same organization and methodological support as traditional classroom work. The most promising technology in this direction today is the use of the Internet, and one of the forms of independent work of students is distance learning [1]. The use of effective techniques and teaching methods, the inclusion of students in an independent creative process is the best way to find the internal reserves of the educational process in the student's personality. It is on this basis that we can talk about the intensification of the educational process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The distance learning system consists of a complex of software and hardware, methodological and organizational measures, which allows you to create individual and group programs in areas and specialties, taking into account modern requirements, including the requirements of third-generation educational standards, as well as testing knowledge on computer systems. - tyam through the Internet.

To organize independent study work of students using Internet technologies, the university has organized a portal based on the ELEARNING SERVER software product.

This system is easy to use, does not require special skills and knowledge and can be used by students from the first semester of study.

The basis for the formation of distance learning is the availability of all educational and methodological materials on electronic media, that is, electronic support for traditional learning is also support for distance learning. Introducing e-learning courses into independent work of students, it is also necessary to organize a library in which all educational materials will be placed in electronic form - lectures, teaching and methodological manuals, reference books, control tests, options for tasks for individual work. This enables students to print any educational information from the library's electronic resources. In combination with traditional teaching aids, it allows you to create a modern educational and methodological complex.

The main content element of the educational process is the training course, which, for the convenience of studying, can be divided into blocks (semesters). ELEARNING SERVER provides the following features for the course [1]:

- management of the educational process;
- distribution of access rights;

- differentiation of interaction between the participants of the educational process;
- education;
- control and evaluation of knowledge. The course includes:
 - content - a structured hypertext textbook containing systematized material within the framework of the program of the academic discipline. The electronic study guide is designed to study the subject from scratch;
 - communicative part - a forum of questions and answers;
 - control part - self-testing tests.

The testing system includes theoretical and practical tests of various types:

- one correct answer;
- several correct answers;
- free answers.

Thus, the time interval from the issuance of the assignment to its verification is reduced, the student does not have to wait two weeks to clarify errors in the performance of homework and graphic works, and then another two weeks to check the corrected work. Students who have missed one or more classroom classes through the distance learning system can, at a convenient time for themselves, get access to educational and methodological materials and independently master the missed material, test their knowledge, complete missed home tasks, graphic works, send them to the teacher for verification and get advice without waiting for the next class. All this helps a student who missed classes, for one reason or another, not to break away from the educational process, not to lose contact with the university and catch up with his classmates as quickly as possible. That is, the interactivity of distance learning using the ELEARNING SERVER in the independent work of students is evident [2].

From the point of view of pedagogy, the student must first be organized for training, then he must perceive and think over the information received, then master the ways of applying new knowledge and subject it to control (self-control). For independent work, such qualities from a student as responsibility and diligence are necessary. One desire to get a higher education is not enough, one must have the will to learn. Independent work on the basis of Internet technologies involves the activation of educational and cognitive activity of students, in which such opportunities and reserves of the individual can be realized, which under normal conditions are not always manifested. In this process, the role of the teacher is important, how he organizes the learning process, how interesting the educational material is presented and what conditions are created for the formation of cognitive interest in the study of the subject. The task of the teacher is to create conditions for the formation of motivation for independent learning activities, which should be based on the interests and needs of the students themselves, help them develop such qualities as the ability to introspection and self-management and find in each student his strongest side, support faith in your own strength [4].

The introduction of distance courses into full-time education does not give students the right not to attend lectures and practical classes at all, these courses are aimed at organizing independent work, actively involving students in the process of obtaining knowledge, and improving academic performance.

CONCLUSION

The use of distance courses in the system of full-time education allows us to highlight a number of positive aspects that ensure the effectiveness of distance learning as a form of independent work of students. Based on taking into account the individual needs of trainees, maximum differentiation and individualization of training is achieved, needs for independent acquisition of knowledge and skills develop, self-learning skills are formed, the time for studying is reduced, without compromising quality, communication skills are formed [2].

Thus, distance courses, which are interactive forms of learning, contribute to the activation of the educational process, including the process of independent work of students.

REFERENCES:

1. Maksimov P. V. Ways of implementation of educational technologies using information and communication technologies and distance learning in regional universities // Actual problems of science: Sat. scientific tr. Based on the materials of the International Scientific and Practical. conf. At 6 p.m. Part 4. Tambov, 2018. P. 94–95.
2. Kanavo V. Advantages and disadvantages of distance learning via the Internet // Business education. 2019
3. Kuznetsova Z.M. Fisenko G.S. Quality management of distance education // Fundamental research. – 2016.
4. Zaichenko T.P. Fundamentals of Distance Learning: Theoretical and Practical Basis: Textbook. - St. Petersburg: Publishing house of the Russian State Pedagogical University im. A.I. Herzen, 2014. - 167 p.